

**Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming
and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets**

Deliverable D8.4

First batch of 10 Practice abstracts

DOCUMENT/REPORT/PUBLIC

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Summary

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VERSION	Version 1

History of Changes

VERSION 0.1	21/02/2025	Boglarka Bozsogi (IFOAM EU)	First draft
VERSION 0.2	21/02/2025	Ambra De Simone (IFOAM EU)	Revisions
VERSION 0.3	26/02/2025	Boglarka Bozsogi (IFOAM EU)	Final draft
VERSION 1	27/02/2025	Ambra De Simone (IFOAM EU)	Submission

Executive Summary

OrganicTargets4EU is a Horizon Europe project dedicated to supporting the European Union's Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies, which aim to have at least 25% of the EU's agricultural land under organic farming and a significant increase in organic aquaculture by 2030.

The project develops a range of possible scenarios for achieving the 25% organic targets and propose possible pathways of change. The socio-economic impacts of reaching the 25% organic target are analysed at two strands:

- **Production and Markets:** Assess where the increases in organic farmland can be achieved and the socio-economic impact of these increases in primary production, value chains, and markets and the mechanisms that can drive demand for organic food.
- **Knowledge and Innovation:** Identify opportunities to strengthen advisory services and in-conversion and capacity building, increase and coordinate research and innovation investments for organic farming, and work towards an innovation ecosystem fit for achieving the Farm to Fork Strategy's targets.

This deliverable is part of the **knowledge and innovation** strand of the project aiming to foster the availability of advisory services and capacity building for organic value chain actors. For that, the OrganicTargets4EU project delivers twenty practice abstracts in total under Task 8.3 Content production. The practice abstracts will be two batches of ten each, targeting farmers, advisors, and organic actors with practical recommendations.

This is the first batch of ten practice abstracts focusing on **organic agriculture knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) and knowledge and innovation systems for organic aquaculture (KIS)** in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from research on marketing strategies to increase demand for organic products ([Deliverable 4.1 Report on Assortment Change and Active Marketing Effects on Demand Pattern](#)).

1. Introduction

The objective of this deliverable is to provide actionable recommendations to practitioners, farmers and advisors, on specific issues related to the organic agricultural knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) or knowledge and innovation systems for organic aquaculture (KIS) in the focus countries or regions. Practice abstracts hope to enable users to learn from the practical experiences of peers, answer concrete questions, provide good practice examples, and open connections with local AKIS actors.

The practice abstracts follow the EIP-AGRI common format and will be available on the [OrganicTargets4EU project website](#), [Organic Eprints](#) (with the permalink placed at the bottom of each practice abstract), the [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) platform, and the [EU CAP Network](#) website with open access for practitioners and the public.

As put by the EU CAP Network, practice abstracts in the EIP-AGRI common format:

- help projects share their results in an easily understandable way for farmers, foresters, rural communities and others from practice
- foster knowledge flows, and shares project results more widely and at a faster pace
- support the development of project proposals with added value, avoiding duplication of ongoing or completed projects
- facilitate networking by connecting project partners with farmers, foresters and others from practice
- answer to real needs from the field

2. Methodology

The OrganicTargets4EU project develops a range of possible scenarios for achieving the 25% organic targets and propose possible pathways of change. The socio-economic impacts of reaching the 25% organic target are analysed at two strands:

- **Production and Markets:** Assess where the increases in organic farmland can be achieved and the socio-economic impact of these increases in primary production, value chains, and markets and the mechanisms that can drive demand for organic food.
- **Knowledge and Innovation:** Identify opportunities to strengthen advisory services and in-conversion and capacity building, increase and coordinate research and innovation investments for organic farming, and work towards an innovation ecosystem fit for achieving the Farm to Fork Strategy's targets.

This deliverable is part of the **knowledge and innovation** strand of the project aiming to foster the availability of advisory services and capacity building for organic value chain actors. For that, the OrganicTargets4EU project delivers twenty practice abstracts in total under Task 8.3 Content production. The practice abstracts will be two batches of ten each, targeting farmers, advisors, and organic actors with practical recommendations.

This deliverable comes from the work that practice partners have been doing with communities of practice and advisory service workshops under WP5 Knowledge exchange and capacity building. The practice abstracts summarise the results of these consultation and collaboration processes in a user-friendly format.

The practice partners from the seven organic agricultural focus countries, the two organic aquaculture focus countries and AU/MAPP leader of WP4 Socio-economic impact on the market side authored the first ten practice abstracts. The project coordinator IFOAM Organics Europe coordinated the production of the practice abstracts providing guidelines (0), the template based on the EIP-AGRI common format (**Figure 1**). The practice partners submitted drafts outlining the problem, the solution, its benefits, and practical recommendations. The review process by IFOAM EU ensured the recommendations to be feasible and actionable for practitioners. Most of the practice abstracts disseminate a list of trusted organic AKIS actors to contact in a given country, essential for farmers who need support in converting to organic or improving their organic practices. Other practice abstracts share good regional practices to be implemented in other relevant contexts.

ORGANIC TARGETS 4EU Add logo organization PRACTICE ABSTRACT

((Title of the method/approach (max. 150 characters))

Problem (approx. 150 characters)
((Describe the problem being addressed in 1-2 sentences. Include a reference to economic and/or ecological impact)).

Solution (approx. 150 characters)
((Describe the presented approach to the solution in 1-2 sentences. Mention under what conditions the practice was developed and tested)).

Benefits (approx. 150 characters)
This practice abstract lists current trusted providers of organic advisory services for farmers in transition to organic in Hungary.

Practical recommendations (approx. 800 characters)
(Describe the step-by-step procedure for proper implementation of the method. Include photos or graphs, if possible and useful.).

Applicability box

Theme
((See Annex for list of themes to choose from, maximum 5))

Keywords
((See Annex for list of keywords to choose from, maximum 5))

Context
(e.g. geographical coverage, climatic limitations, other)

Application time (if relevant)
((Indicate the time of year/season when the method/practice can be applied))

Required time (if relevant)
((Indicate the amount of time required to implement the practice))

Period of impact (if relevant)
((Indicate the period of time in which an impact is expected))

Equipment (if relevant)
((required machinery, if applicable))

Best in (if relevant)
((Indicate in which type of system/with which method is best practiced))

ORGANIC TARGETS 4EU PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Insert picture here (formatting will be done by the Organic Farm Knowledge editing team). Make sure you reference the picture in the recommendations ("In Picture 1, you can see" etc.)
((Image caption)). Photo: ((indicate who took the picture))

Further information

Videos

- Check the following video ((indicate title, put a hyperlink to the site and underline it)) for further instructions ((indicate language)).

Further reading

- ((refer to existing technical guides, handbooks etc.))

Weblinks

- Check the Organic Farm Knowledge platform [hyperlink] for more practical recommendations.
- ((refer to other websites))

Other useful links:

-

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher(s):
((Institute name (abbreviation)
Address, postal code, city
Phone, website))

Author: ((names of the authors))
Contact: ((email address of the first author))

QR code will be added by the OFK editing team

Review: ((added later by OFK or project editing team))
Format: Organic-farmknowledge.org/toolbox
Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets
Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2024

Figure 1 Practice Abstract template based on the EIP-AGRI Common Format

2.1 Practice abstract (PA) writing roadmap

The procedure informs about the three steps (draft, revision and finalization) and indicates the responsible beneficiary. Once a partner submitted the draft of a practice abstract, IFOAM EU does a first quality check and revision and sent it back to the authors for the implementation of the requested changes. The review process by IFOAM EU ensured the recommendations to be feasible and actionable for practitioners, that the information is clear and concise as well as visually attractive and easy to navigate. This step is repeated several times until the draft is of high-quality content and fulfils all EIP-AGRI and OFK platform eligibility requirements. Below the three steps of the production process:

Colour code indicating action required by: **Coordinator**; **Authors**; **Reviewers**

Step 1: Draft (approx. 14 days from the writing request)

- **(Ambra De Simone) and Boglarka Bozsogi** send the writing request with relative deadlines to the project partners responsible for writing the PA
- **The author** prepares a draft of the Practice Abstract (PA) in the correct template (OT4EU_PA_Template.docx). Remember to create a copy.
- The responsible **author** sends the PA draft to (ambra.desimone@organicseurope.bio, boglarka.bozsogi@organicseurope.bio and susannepadel@outlook.com).

Step 2: Revision (approx. 1 month)

- **Boglarka Bozsogi** reviews the PA for quality criteria, clarity, and compliance with template and sends it to the responsible **reviewers**, if applicable.
- **Reviewers** check for content eligibility and send it to **(Ambra De Simone) and Boglarka Bozsogi** and **authors**
- **Authors** implement reviewers' suggestions and send the revised version to **(Ambra De Simone) and Boglarka Bozsogi** (ambra.desimone@organicseurope.bio, boglarka.bozsogi@organicseurope.bio and susannepadel@outlook.com). The previous steps are repeated, if needed.
- **Boglarka Bozsogi** sends the PA to **authors** for further implementation of suggestions, if any.

Step 3: Finalization (within 14 days after revision)

- **(Ambra De Simone) and Boglarka Bozsogi** makes a final check, finalises the layout and send it to the **authors** for approval. Approval should be provided within 5 working days. No response within the 5 working days, will be considered as approved.
- **(Ambra De Simone) and Boglarka Bozsogi** upload the PAs on the [Organic Eprints - Welcome to Organic Eprints](#) and [Home - Organic Farm Knowledge](#) and with the project communication leader (CONSULAI) for dissemination.

3. First batch of 10 Practice Abstracts

This is the first batch of ten practice abstracts focusing on **organic agriculture knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS)** in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), and **knowledge and innovation systems for organic aquaculture (KIS)** in two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from research on marketing strategies to increase demand for organic products ([Deliverable 4.1 Report on Assortment Change and Active Marketing Effects on Demand Pattern](#)).

This section includes a table of the first batch of practice abstracts, the consortium partner that authored it, and the focus country, as well as the practice abstracts themselves as uploaded individually to the [OrganicTargets4EU project website](#), [Organic Eprints](#), and the [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) platform.

Practice abstract title	Author	Country	Permalink
Active Marketing Strategies Driving Organic Buying Behaviour in EU Supermarkets	AU/MAPP	Europe	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54927
Actors of knowledge and innovation systems (KIS) for organic aquaculture in Greece	AUTH	GR	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54930
Conversion to organic navigation guide for Austrian farmers	LKNO	AU	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54929
Developing cross-regional natural resource corporations	Naturland	DE	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54948
Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) actors in Hungary	ÖMKi	HU	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54924
Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in France	ITAB	FR	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54932
Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Italy	CIHEAM Bari	IT	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54946
Organic conversion checks: a Danish strategy for upscaling organic farming	ICOEL	DK	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54947
Organic Knowledge and Innovation System (KIS) for aquaculture in Germany	Naturland	DE	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54934
Regional clusters of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Romania	Inter-Bio	RO	Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54931

Table 1 First batch of 10 practice abstracts

Active Marketing Strategies Driving Organic Buying Behaviour in EU Supermarkets

Problem

Limited consumer demand for organic products challenges the EU's goal of increasing organic farming to 25% of agricultural land by 2030.

Solution

Active marketing strategies such as information labels, nudges, product assortment changes and brand strategies can effectively raise demand for organic products in supermarkets.

Benefits

Promotes consumer awareness and demand for organic products, aligns with EU sustainability goals, provides guide for scaling organic market growth.

Practical recommendations

The following marketing strategies were found useful in increasing the demand for organic products:

Use of information labels:

- In addition to labelling organic products with the well-known EU organic label, the introduction of a prospective EU climate label could positively influence consumer demand for organic products. However, further research is needed to determine whether this climate label enhances the value proposition of organic products.

Use of nudging:

- Retailers can label organic products as "Popular Choice" or "Bestseller", leveraging social norms to encourage consumers to change their organic buying behaviour.

Use of assortment changes:

- Expanding the assortment of organic products relative to conventional ones may be used to effectively increase demand for organic products.

Use of brand strategy:

- The introduction of premium-oriented private label brands for organic products effectively drives organic product demand, presenting a potentially impactful alternative to both conventional budget-oriented private labels and premium brands.

Applicability box

Theme

Marketing and agricultural trade
Standards, regulations and certification

Keywords: Marketing strategies, Assortment changes, Organic buying behaviour

Context

Tested across Denmark, Italy, Germany, and Romania, representing diverse EU consumer preferences and varying cultural contexts.

Period of impact

Short- to long-term (e.g., behavioural shifts may occur immediately, with potential for sustained impacts if strategies are reinforced).

Best in

Retail environments (e.g., convenience stores)

Further information

Further reading

- [D4.1 Report on Assortment Change and Active Marketing Effects on Demand Patterns](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher(s): MAPP Centre, Aarhus University (AU)
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Permalink: [Organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54927](https://organic-farmknowledge.org/tool/54927)

Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2025

Actors of knowledge and innovation systems (KIS) for organic aquaculture in Greece

Problem

The Greek organic advisory system has limited access to information on organic aquaculture and lacks personalised, specialised technical support for fish farmers transitioning to organic methods.

Solution

This practice abstract lists current providers of organic advisory services for fish farmers in transition to organic in Greece (Figure 1).

Benefits

KIS for organic aquaculture thrives on several dedicated actors supporting the development of organic farming providing technical support, administrative assistance, and trainings. Farmers seeking advice on specific topics can contact the organisations recommended in this practice abstract.

Applicability box

Theme

Organic Aquaculture management - Standards, regulations and certification

Keywords

Organic advisory services, conversion factors, KIS, advisory service

Context

Greece

Practical recommendations

- **Technical support:** Support in the transition phase with a focus on professional and technical areas, and with opportunities for collaboration in co-creation, Living Labs, and on-farm experiments: Hellenic Centre for Marine Research, Hellenic Agricultural Organization-ELGO Dimitra
- **Information on organic certification requirements:** Certification bodies (Agrocet, BioHellas, TÜVHellas)
- **Free or low-cost training programmes** on organic farming at different levels of the education system: Universities (e.g., Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, Agricultural University of Athens, University of Patras, University of Thessaly)
- **Administrative assistance:** mainly in the application process for organic subsidies: Advisors working in the network of Geotechnical Chambers of Agriculture, independent advisors.

Figure 1: Who can fish farmers turn for advice to on organic aquaculture in Greece?

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Further information

Videos

- [Hellenic Aquaculture Producers Organisation](#)
- [Greek organic aquaculture - European Aquaculture Society talk \(EAS\)](#)

Further reading

- [National National Strategic Plan on Aquaculture \(GR\)](#)
- [Hellenic Aquaculture Producers Organisation](#)

Weblinks

- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

Other useful links:

- [Ministry of Rural Development and Food](#)
- [Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Veterinary Medicine, Laboratory of Aquaculture and Aquatic Animal diseases](#)
- [Hellenic Centre of Marine Research \(HCMR\)](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

Publisher(s): Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, School of Veterinary Medicine, Laboratory of Aquaculture and Aquatic Animal Diseases
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Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

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Conversion to organic navigation guide for Austrian farmers

Problem

Once a farmer decides to convert to organic, the needed steps and paperwork may seem complex.

Solution

In Austria, various institutions offer advisory services as well as a broad range of courses and trainings for farmers in conversion to organic. This practice abstract sets out steps to take and to give an overview of actors that can provide assistance (Figure 1).

Benefits

This practice abstract lists current trusted providers of organic advisory services for farmers who want to convert to organic production in Austria as well as all important actors involved in the process.

Practical recommendations

The legal basis of organic standards is the EU regulation 2018/484.

- **Pre conversion information:** Regional agricultural chambers and the organic farmers association Bio Austria offer **Individual farm consultancy** and organic farm visit opportunities.
- Websites with information about organic farming principles and standards:
 - www.lko.at/Bio
 - www.bio-austria.at
 - www.erde-saat.at
 - www.demeter.at
 - www.oekolandbau.de
 - www.fibl.org
 - www.bio-net.at
- **Sign certification contract:** Certification bodies are private service providers accredited to conduct organic certifications. To start the transitioning process farmers can choose one of the following certification bodies: ABG, BIOS, LACON, SGS, SLK, LKV. The certification body will once a year conduct an on-farm inspection visit to assure that the organic standards are followed. A conversion time of 24 months (or 36 months for permanent crops) must pass until the farm products can be labelled as certified organic.
- **Allowed inputs:** Organic farm management means that operating resources are restricted according to Regulation (EU) 2018/484. Permitted inputs such as fertilisers, pesticides, or feed stuff with approval for organic farming are listed in the Austrian catalogue of permitted inputs.

Applicability box

Theme

Conversion to organic – standards, regulations, certification and advanced training

Keywords

Conversion, control agency, advisory service, further education

Context

Austria

- **Seed and planting material:** Only organic seeds and planting material are allowed in organic farming. A list of available organic seed lots for Austria can be found in the Austrian Organic Seed Database.
- **Advanced training:** LFI, Bio Austria, FIBL, Demeter provide advanced trainings.

The basic steps of conversion to organic

Figure 1 - basic steps of conversion to organic

Further information

Further reading

- [Guide to becoming an organic farmer](#)
- [Conversion to organic arable farming](#)
- [Information about conversion times](#)
- [Guide for conversion of grassland and animal husbandry](#)

Weblinks

- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2024

Developing cross-regional natural resource corporations

Problem

One of the undeveloped areas in the organic advisory service in Germany is the regional management of natural resources such as water, biodiversity, and climate.

Solution

The development of regional cooperations by organic farmers, public service providers such as water companies, and the private sector where farmers are embedded in programs for the provision of public services.

Benefits

A regional approach can help maintain important natural resources (climate, water, biodiversity) ensuring long-term productivity and food security. Farmers are encouraged to maintain their organic production through support in marketing and cooperation with a public service provider.

Applicability box

Theme

Soil, environment and society, cross-regional development

Keywords

Environment, society, biodiversity conservation, climate change adaptation, sustainability

Context

Germany

Period of impact

Continuously, starting about two years after the first actions

Practical recommendations

Farmers and advisors in a region should reach out to their water companies or other public service providers to suggest setting up similar programs. Value chain managers and people working with Öko-Modell-Regions should also approach service providers and private companies in their region to establish regional cooperation. On the practical side, it is important to develop a system that is a win-win solution for all involved stakeholders. Ideally, farmers receive a payment for the organic production through a programme, e.g., from the water company that is additional to the CAP payments. The combination of value chain analysis and marketing products with a positive effect on public resources, e.g., groundwater, can establish a strong network for organic transition and long-term production.

Further information

Weblinks

- [Öko Landbau](#)
- [OÖWV | Projekte | Das Blaue Land](#)
- [Ökologischer Landbau | Initiative Ökobauern | SWM](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2024

Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) actors in Hungary

Problem

The Hungarian organic advisory system lacks independent, personalised advisory services with cross-regional specialisation and comprehensive coverage available to support farmers in the transition to organic.

Solution

The organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Hungary relies on several dedicated actors supporting organic farming development with technical support, administrative assistance, and trainings.

Benefits

This practice abstract lists current trusted providers of organic advisory services for farmers in transition to organic in Hungary (Figure 1).

Applicability box

Theme

Farm management - Standards, regulations and certification

Keywords

Organic advisory services, conversion factors, AKIS, advisory service

Context

Hungary

Practical recommendations for strengthening the organic advisory services

The following organisations are recommended for farmers to contact for advice:

Technical support:

- Personalised support in the transition phase with a focus on professional and technical areas and opportunities for collaboration in co-creation, Living Labs, and on-farm experiments: Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (ÖMKi).
- Advice and participation in on-site trials to measure and improve the efficiency of organic plant protection products: Manufacturers, e.g., Biocont Kft.

Information on certification requirements: Certification bodies (Biokontroll Hungária Kft., Bio Garancia Kft.) and the Organic Farming Association (Magyar Biokultúra Szövetség).

Strengthening the innovation network: EU CAP Network led by the Institute of Agricultural Economics (AKI).

Free or low-cost training programmes on organic farming at different levels of the education system: Universities (e.g., MATE, Debrecen University, Széchenyi István University).

Administrative assistance: mainly in the application process for organic subsidies: Advisors working in the network of Chamber of Agriculture, independent advisors.

Figure 1: Who can farmers turn to for advice in Hungary?

Further information

Videos

- [Biokontroll Hungária Nonprofit Kft.'s YouTube channel: General information on the transition to organic \(HU\).](#)
- [ÖMKi's video on the National Action Plan for the Development of Organic Farming \(Az új Nemzeti Cselekvési Terv az Ökológiai Gazdálkodás Fejlesztéséért \(Ágazati Nap 2022\)\), \(HU\).](#)
- [ÖMKi's video on Knowledge transfer and expert advice in the new CAP, \(Tudásátadás és szaktanácsadás az új KAP-ban \(Ágazati Nap 2022\)\), \(HU\).](#)

Further reading

- [National Action Plan for the Development of Organic Farming \(HU\).](#)

Weblinks

- Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge platform](#) for more practical recommendations.

Other useful links

- [Research Institute of Organic Agriculture \(ÖMKi\)](#)
- [Chamber of Agriculture - about the advisory network](#)
- [Organic Farming Association; Bio Garancia Kft. Documents - information documents and forms](#)
- [Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences \(MATE\)](#)
- [University of Debrecen \(DU\) - Faculty of Agricultural and Food Sciences and Environmental Management](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Project info: This practice abstract was elaborated by OrganicTargets4EU / Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

Project website: <https://organictargets.eu/> © 2024

Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in France

Problem

The organic AKIS in France needs to deconstruct silos to better share knowledge among public and private actors and advise the whole value chain from production to market, retail, and processing (Figure 1).

Solution

This practice abstract lists AKIS actors that provide support with funding and administrative help, plant protection strategies, regulation advice, and more.

Applicability box

Theme

Training, technical & marketing support, and administrative assistance for organic farming

Keywords

Organic advisory services, AKIS, organic training

Context

France

Benefits

Farmers can reach out to trusted providers of organic advisory services.

Practical recommendations

This practice abstract lists the types of AKIS actors with linked examples that farmers can turn to, based on the results of a French AKIS workshop evaluating availability, competences, and affordability of organic advisory services.

1. **Agricultural technical institutes:** Arvalis, Terres Inovia, GAB, FNAB, ITAB, IFV
2. **Chambers of Agriculture**
3. **Producer groups with a facilitator**
4. **Regional experimentation platforms:** GRAB
5. **Advisors and independent consultant:** CETA
6. **Digital platform:** Triple Performance, GECO, R&D Agri, agroecologie.org
7. **Social media**
8. **Start up or other independent organisation:** Ver de terre production, fermes d'avenir, Solagro
9. **Public and government players:** Agence Bio, Community of municipalities
10. **Cooperatives and producer groups**
11. **French agricultural research institute:** INRAe
12. **The agricultural education system**
13. **Certification bodies:** INAO, Ecocert
14. **Specialised press, information bulletins**
15. **Fellow farmer**

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et de l'alimentation biologiques

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

Further information

Further reading

- [OrganicTargets4EU Deliverable 5.2 Analysis of barriers of conversion and recommendations for strengthening organic advisory services and capacity building](#)
- [France–Organic Sector AKIS Factsheet](#)
- [ITAB, “Synergies bio & non bio” for knowledge improvement support for organic farming \(FR\)](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Organic Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Italy

Problem

The Italian organic advisory system includes various networks and trusted, internationally connected groups, organisations, and institutional structures, of renowned expertise but lacks a unified system for training, technical, marketing, and administrative support tailored to the organic sector's needs.

Solution

Implement a virtual hub to share information about training opportunities, contents, methods, and tools for providers of technical & marketing support and legal-administrative assistance in organic farming. The platform to be hosted by SINAB portal is included in the National Action Plan (NAP).

Applicability box

Theme

Training, technical & marketing support, and administrative assistance for organic farming

Keywords

Organic advisory services, AKIS, organic training

Context

Italy

Benefits

The hub fosters:

- Comprehensive and coordinated trainings across the national territory to develop the organic farming sector
- Professional organic advisers' knowledge and skills.
- Impactful collaboration and partnerships between organic AKIS actors operating at national and regional level to meet the sector's evolving challenges.

Practical recommendations for AKIS actors

- Seek out peer-to-peer coordination and collaboration to build up a comprehensive and integrated information base
- Promote horizontal support for organic AKIS rather than for separate sub-systems
- Invest in increasing expertise addressing multiple aspects of organic farming
- Adopt a demand-driven approach organic advisory services
- Ensure structured and continuous provision of organic advisory services and the adoption of more participatory and innovative methods and tools
- Implement the virtual hub to create a reference point for Italian organic operators and stakeholders

Main AKIS actors supporting organic farming development in Italy (Source: Italian NOAP 2024-2026):

Organisation	Type	Members	AKIS functions
AIAB	producer association	producers, consultants, citizens	research, training, dissemination, consultancy
ANABIO	producer association	producers, technical advisors, consultants	research, experimentation, training, dissemination, assistance, consultancy
Associazione Agricoltura Biodinamica	producer association	operators, experts	training, dissemination, consultancy

PRACTICE ABSTRACT

AssoBio	processors and retailers association	operators, experts	dissemination, information, consultancy
ATBio	consultants and inspectors association	consultants, inspectors	information, training, dissemination
Bioagricoop	association for promotion	operators, experts	dissemination, research and innovation
Bioqualità	network of consultants	consultants	training, consultancy
Coldiretti Bio	producer association	producers, technical advisors, consultants	research, experimentation, dissemination, assistance and consultancy
CopagriBio	producer association	producers, technical advisors, consultants	research, experimentation, dissemination, assistance and consultancy
Federbio	interprofessional federation	producers, technical advisors, researchers	training, dissemination, consultancy
FIRAB	scientific association	researchers, experts	experimentation, action-research, farmer to farmer exchanges, dissemination
GRAB-IT	scientific association	researchers, experts	research, experimentation, professional scientific & technical support, dissemination
RIRAB	scientific association	researchers, experts	research and innovation

Further information

Further reading

- National Organic Action Plan (IT)

Weblinks

- Sistema di Informazione Nazionale per l'Agricoltura Biologica (SINAB)*: information platform about organic farming running since the year 2000 and a reference point for Italian organic operators and stakeholders.
- Check the Organic Farm Knowledge platform for more practical recommendations.

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Organic conversion checks: a Danish strategy for upscaling organic farming

Problem

The goal of the Danish government is to double the organic area by 2030. That requires more farmers to convert to organic and existing organic areas to stay organic.

Solution

Denmark's organic action plan promotes organic farming through upscaling and market growth. Farmers considering conversion can get a free conversion check from the Fund for Organic Farming.

Benefits

During the conversion check an experienced organic farm advisor from the Innovation Centre for Organic Farming (ICOEL) or another advisory service provider visits the farm. The consultant and the farmer go through the farm's production and sales potential of converting to organic production. Farmers can ask questions and explore development opportunities, helping them make informed decisions. The approach has proven to cause fewer re-conversions or interrupted processes.

Applicability box

Theme

Conversion to organic farming

Keywords

Organic advisory service, Farm visit, practical and economic advice

Context

This methodology can be adapted to any geographical contexts and availability of resources.

Required time

The farm visit should take around 2 hours approximately.

Practical recommendations

- The farmer **contacts** the advisory services or ICOEL to ask for a conversion check. This can also take place on the initiative of a municipality for all farms in the region.
- **Before the visit**, the farmer receives a simple questionnaire, so that the conversion advisor can prepare.
- The **advisor** has experience with the farm type (e.g., livestock, arable, vegetable). Impartiality and professionalism are key.
- The **farm visit of** approx. 2 hours includes:
 - Review of fields and stables to assess the opportunities and barriers for organic production and how to overcome them
 - Discussion of rules for organic production in general and for the specific farm type
 - Financial estimate based on the current production and potential subsidies
 - Market and sales opportunities
 - A timeline for conversion
- The advisor provides a **report** with a realistic assessment of the farm's suitability for organic farming.
- If the farmer decides to convert to organic, the advisor will guide him through the process. Conversion to organic takes around 2-3 years to be effective.

Picture 1: Conversion check farm visit to a mixed farming system. (Jakob Brandt)

Picture 2: Conversion check farm visit to a free-range swine production system (Joachim Kjeldsen)

Picture 3: Conversion check farm visit to a cattle production system (Joachim Kjeldsen)

Further information

Further reading

- Strategy for organics. Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries. December 2023.
- Manual for conversion checks

Weblinks

- Check the Organic Farm Knowledge platform for more practical recommendations
- Conversion to organic: professional meetings and networks (Omlægning til økologi – faglige møder og netværk (DK))

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Organic Knowledge and Innovation System (KIS) for aquaculture in Germany

Problem

The German aquaculture sector lacks access to independent, personalised advisory services to support fish farmers in the transition to organic farm management.

Solution

Improve the knowledge transfer from research institutions to practitioners (farmers, advisors etc.) and provide an information platform of actors supporting organic aquaculture development with technical support, administrative assistance, and trainings.

Benefits

This practice abstract lists current trusted providers of organic aquaculture advisory services and technical support for fish farmers in transition to organic farm management in Germany.

Applicability box

Theme

Organic aquaculture management - Standards, regulations and certification

Keywords

Organic advisory services, conversion factors, KIS, advisory service, aquaculture

Context

Germany

Practical recommendations

Fish farmers are recommended to contact the following organisations for advice. Web links are provided.

Private associations & organizations for organic farming & aquaculture

- Naturland e.V.
- Bioland e.V.
- Verband der deutschen Binnenfischerei und Aquakultur e.V. (VDBA) (Association of German Inland Fisheries and Aquaculture)
- Der Bundesverband Aquakultur e.V.
- Öko-Insitut e.V. (Institute for Applied Ecology)

Research & education organizations

- Bayerische Landesanstalt für Landwirtschaft – Institut für Fischerei (Bavarian State Research Center for Agriculture – Institute for fisheries)
- University of Veterinary Medicine Hannover
- Alfred-Wegener-Institut (AWI)
- Thünen-Institute
- Verband der Fischereiverwaltung und Fischereiwissenschaft e.V. (Association of fisheries management and fisheries science)
- IGB – Leibniz Institute of Freshwater Ecology and Inland Fisheries
- Forschungsinstitut für biologischen Landbau FiBL

Inspection bodies for organic aquaculture

- Lacon Insitut
- Abcert
- Grünstempel – Ökoprüfstelle e.V.
- GfRS Gesellschaft für Ressourcenschutz mbH

Public authorities

- Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture (BMEL)
- Federal Office for Agriculture and Food (BLE)
- Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF)
- Governments/authorities in the individual federal states, especially State Agricultural Offices

Further information

Videos

- [Biofisch und ökologische Fischzucht im Kreislauf der Natur – Marc Mößmers Teichgut Haslau. \(Organic fish production in the cycle of nature \(DE\)\)](#)

Further reading

- [National strategic plan for aquaculture in Germany \(NASTAQ\)](#)
- [Regulatory requirements for organic aquaculture](#)
- [Organic Aquaculture in the EU](#)
- [Bundesanstalt für Landwirtschaft und Ernährung \(Perspectives for the German aquaculture sector in the international competition \(DE\)\) \(BLE\) 2017. Perspektiven für die deutsche Aquakultur im internationalen Wettbewerb. Abschlussbericht. Stand September 2017. Online](#)

Weblinks

- [Government funding opportunities](#)
- [List of accredited organic certification bodies in Germany](#)
- [Naturland aquaculture](#)

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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Regional clusters of Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation System (AKIS) in Romania

Problem

Romania lacks a specialised network of organic advisors with sectorial or regional focus and has a high reconversion rate from organic to conventional.

Solution

Regional clusters address issues across the value chain, share knowledge, host workshops, and allocate subject-matter advisors to farmers' needs (Table 1).

Benefits

Clusters help farmers gain funding or technical advice. Regional networks addressing local needs strengthen community cohesion and the organic narrative nationally.

Applicability box

Theme

Farm management - Standards, regulations and certification

Keywords

Organic AKIS, integrated services, communities of practice CoP and clusters

Context

Romania

Period of impact (If relevant)

Long term

Practical recommendations/results

Farmers in Romania who are organic, are interested or want to convert to organic, should join one the following existing clusters in their region:

Table 1 Regional clusters in Romania

Logo	Name (link to website)	Logo	Name (link to website)
	Cluster Bio Oltenia		
	Bio Concept Valea Prahovei Cluster		
	BioNest Cluster		

AKIS should work with communities at the regional level to scale organic, emulating similar initiatives, e.g., biodistricts in Italy or Living Labs. Bio-districts in Italy or Living Labs.

Photos: Activities of Romanian clusters. Source: Inter-Bio.

About the cluster

The Romanian cluster-based approach focusses on identifying regional needs, recognising the significant variations in sector-specific value chains across different areas. The cluster communities were established after 2015 and further strengthened through a Swiss-Romanian program (2017–2019) aimed at enhancing the export capacity of organic farmers in Romania. It identifies and addresses key needs such as fertilizer knowledge, business startup inputs, conversion processes, market strategy, and crop rotation. As facilitators, we provide tailored support whether advising on exports or connecting farmers for peer learning. The community organizes workshops to tackle these topics effectively. It advocates for a one-stop advisory approach, recognizing the value of integrated services.

Further information

Weblinks

[Ministry of Agriculture and Rural Development Romania](#)

[National Network for Rural Development Romania](#)

Check the [Organic Farm Knowledge](#) platform for more practical recommendations

About this practice abstract and the OrganicTargets4EU project

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4. Conclusion

The first batch of ten practice abstract from the OrganicTargets4EU project focuses on organic agriculture and aquaculture knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS) in the seven focus countries on agriculture (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Romania), two focus countries on aquaculture (Germany, Greece), in addition to results from research on marketing strategies to increase demand for organic products. All materials are accessible free of charge on [OrganicFarmKnowledge](#) and the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project website.

To learn more about the project's work related to AKIS, please visit our website, consult our [country factsheets](#), and keep an eye out on further deliverables, publications, and events. The second batch of practice abstracts will be delivered in December 2025 (M40).

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